

Original Research

Financial Technology and Profitability in Tanzanian Commercial Banks: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

This study investigates the influence of financial technology on the profitability of commercial banks in Tanzania, addressing a significant gap in the existing literature. Using a bank FinTech index combined with bank-specific and macroeconomic factors, the analysis covers 30 Tanzanian commercial banks over the period 2010 to 2021. Panel data techniques, specifically the two-step system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator, were employed to assess the effects across large, medium, and small banks. The results indicate a positive relationship between the FinTech index and bank profitability, with a 1% increase in the FinTech index leading to a 0.078% rise in return on assets (ROA) and a 1.596% increase in return on equity (ROE). Large banks demonstrated a stronger response to FinTech development than their smaller, and medium counterparts. The findings have significant implications for policymakers and practitioners. Policymakers, particularly the Bank of Tanzania, should establish a supportive regulatory framework to encourage sustainable FinTech growth and enhance integration across all bank categories. For practitioners, especially in small and medium-sized banks, the study highlights the importance of forming strategic partnerships with FinTech firms and adopting scalable solutions tailored to their operational capacities. The banking sector can achieve improved profitability and financial stability by fostering innovation and aligning technological adoption with bank-specific factors.

Keywords: Bank FinTech index, bank profitability, financial technology, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Amid the Fourth Industrial Revolution, the rise of financial technology (FinTech) has transformed every sector, presenting both challenges and opportunities. The banking sector, which is crucial to the modern economy, is at the forefront of this change (Gomber *et al.*, 2018). FinTech is a technology-driven innovation in financial services, that encompasses mobile and internet banking, artificial intelligence (AI), blockchain, and big data analytics (Donnelly, 2019). These innovations have redefined banking operations, enabling process optimization, cost reduction, and enhanced customer experiences (Mahapatra & Singh, 2021). Bank profitability refers to a bank's ability to generate earnings from its operations, serving as a key indicator of financial health and performance. The Bank of Tanzania (BOT) assesses profitability using measures such as Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE) among others (BOT, 2018). However, while FinTech is rapidly transforming its financial landscape, its precise effect on bank profitability has produced mixed results (Katsiampa *et al.*, 2022; Zhao *et al.*, 2022; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021; Ozili, 2021; Amal, 2020; Berg *et al.*, 2020; Ky *et al.*, 2019).

Globally, FinTech integration within a banking business has yielded varying impacts. In developed economies with robust digital infrastructures, FinTech significantly enhances profitability by creating new revenue streams and improving operational efficiency (Zhao *et al.*, 2022; Phan *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2020). Conversely, in developing regions like Africa, resource limitations, regulatory challenges, and underdeveloped digital ecosystems constrain the profitability gains from FinTech integration (Ediagbonya & Tioluwani, 2023).

Tanzania's banking sector has experienced considerable FinTech development over the last decade. Commercial banks have embraced FinTech through the adoption of digital payment channels, such as Automated Teller Machines (ATMs), point-of-sale (POS) devices, internet banking, and mobile banking. Between 2012 and 2020, the number of ATMs increased from 1,361 to 2,058, and the number of POS devices surged from 1,910 to 47,496 (Bank of Tanzania (BOT), 2019/2020). Additionally, the value of internet banking transactions rose from TZS 17.8 trillion to TZS 64.9 trillion, while mobile banking transactions jumped from TZS 302 million to TZS 25 trillion (Macha & Massawe, 2023).

Furthermore, the banking sector has transformed through key policies, such as the National ICT Policy of 2016, which focuses on enhancing ICT skills, broadband access, and infrastructure. The National Five-Year Development Plan (2021/22–2025/26) further promotes ICT innovation in finance, while the Financial Sector Development Master Plan (2020/21-2029/30) aims to create a stable, inclusive financial system. The National Payments Systems Act of 2015 has also been crucial in regulating digital financial services and fostering FinTech growth in the banking sector (Macha & Massawe, 2023).

Despite these advancements, the relationship between FinTech and bank profitability remains unclear. Other studies have focused on the influence of Fintech products on bank profitability (Chen *et al.*, 2021; Misati *et al.*, 2021; Berg *et al.*, 2020; Ky *et al.*, 2019). Some studies have found that FinTech negatively influences the profitability of

commercial banks (Katsiampa *et al.*, 2022; Zhao *et al.*, 2022; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021; Phan *et al.*, 2020). Other studies have documented that FinTech positively influences the profitability of CBs (Ozili, 2021a; Berg *et al.*, 2020; Misati *et al.*, 2020; Ky *et al.*, 2019; Odawa, 2016), and a few, including Amal (2020) and Wang *et al.*, (2020), found no significant influence of FinTech on the profitability of commercial banks. While FinTech has gained significant attention, research on its influence on bank profitability in Tanzania remains scarce.

This study seeks to bridge this gap by constructing a novel Bank FinTech Index tailored to Tanzanian commercial banks. The index measures the FinTech development of commercial banks and its influence on profitability across large, medium, and small banks. Additionally, the study incorporates both bank-specific factors, such as capital adequacy and cost efficiency, and macroeconomic variables, such as gross domestic product (GDP) growth and inflation, to provide a comprehensive understanding of profitability drivers. Recent empirical works by Alfadli and Rjoub (2020) and Al-Homaidi *et al.* (2018) highlight the importance of integrating these factors for a comprehensive and relevant analysis of profitability drivers.

The primary motivation for this study stems from the rapid digital transformation of the banking sector and the growing importance of FinTech in enhancing operational efficiency and expanding market reach (Barroso and Laborda, 2022). This study aims to answer the following questions: How does the bank FinTech index influence profitability in Tanzanian commercial banks? Does the effect differ by bank category, and what are the broader implications for the banking sector and the effect of bank-specific and macroeconomic factors on the profitability of commercial banks?

The results indicate a significant relationship between the FinTech index and profitability, with larger banks leveraging advanced technologies to achieve operational efficiencies and cost reductions, thereby enhancing profitability as measured by return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). Conversely, smaller banks faced challenges in fully capitalizing on FinTech due to resource constraints, underscoring the need for tailored adoption strategies.

This study contributes to the literature by introducing a novel bank FinTech index for Tanzanian commercial banks that provides a unique measure of FinTech development in the Tanzanian banking sector, addressing a gap in previous research. Furthermore, by exploring the relationship between the bank FinTech index and profitability using both theoretical models and empirical data, this study offers practical insights for policymakers and bank managers to enhance FinTech integration and profitability. These findings contribute to the development of sustainable strategies that support financial growth and stability in Tanzania.

Following this introduction, Section 2 discusses the theoretical and empirical frameworks. Section 3 describes the methodology used in this study. Section 4 presents the results and a detailed discussion, and Section 5 concludes the study with recommendations, policy implications, limitations and areas for further studies.

Literature Review

Theoretical Frameworks

This study examines the relationship between the Bank FinTech Index and bank profitability by integrating two complementary theoretical perspectives: Financial Innovation Theory (FIT) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of FinTech on banking operations and financial performance.

Financial Innovation Theory (FIT), as proposed by Drejer, (2004) based on Schumpeter's early proposition (1934), highlights the crucial role of technological advancements in driving innovation within financial systems. The theory posits that innovations such as blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), and big data analytics transform banking by enabling the creation of new financial products, services, and processes. These advancements enhance operational efficiency, reduce costs, and improve customer experiences, fostering greater customer loyalty and profitability (Kharrat *et al.*, 2024; Del Gaudio *et al.*, 2021). For instance, mobile banking platforms and robo-advisory services provide personalized and accessible financial solutions, expanding banks' reach to underserved markets and opening new revenue streams. However, FIT also acknowledges the challenges associated with FinTech adoption, such as high implementation costs, technological complexity, and evolving regulatory frameworks, which may hinder banks' ability to fully capitalize on these innovations (Awotunde *et al.*, 2021). By emphasizing the need for strategic approaches to FinTech deployment, FIT highlights the balance between technological potential and associated risks, particularly in emerging markets like Tanzania.

Complementing FIT, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), developed by Davis, (1989), provides insights into the behavioral and organizational dimensions of technology adoption. TAM identifies perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU) as critical factors influencing the acceptance and integration of new technologies. In the banking context, these factors determine how effectively FinTech solutions are adopted and utilized by employees and customers. User-friendly and demonstrably beneficial technologies are more likely to gain acceptance, facilitating smoother integration and enabling banks to achieve profitability gains and operational efficiency (Latreche *et al.*, 2024; Isiaku and Adalier, 2024). TAM also sheds light on challenges such as resistance to change and inadequate training, which can impede the successful deployment of FinTech. By addressing these behavioral and organizational barriers, TAM underscores the importance of aligning technological adoption with human and institutional readiness to maximize the impact of FinTech solutions.

Together, FIT and TAM offer a robust framework for understanding the multifaceted relationship between FinTech adoption and profitability. While FIT provides an economic and technological perspective, emphasizing the transformative potential of FinTech, TAM addresses the human and organizational factors critical to successful implementation. This integrated approach is particularly relevant in Tanzania, where resource constraints, regulatory challenges, and diverse market dynamics necessitate tailored strategies for FinTech integration. By combining these theoretical perspectives,

this study provides actionable insights for policymakers and bank managers seeking to enhance profitability through effective FinTech integration.

Empirical Review

The integration of financial technology (FinTech) into the banking sector has significantly reshaped operational processes, introducing innovations such as big data, machine learning, mobile banking, artificial intelligence (AI), and blockchain. These advancements have transformed service delivery, reduced operational costs, and improved customer experiences. For example, Chen *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that the perceived usefulness and ease of use of FinTech products positively impact commercial bank profitability in China. Similarly, Acar and Çıtak (2019) emphasized the importance of integrating FinTech into internal banking operations, highlighting its role in modernizing Turkish banks.

Despite these benefits, the literature reveals contradictory findings regarding the impact of FinTech on bank profitability. While Hasaka (2019) found a positive correlation between FinTech adoption and profitability in ASEAN countries, Phan *et al.*, (2020, 2018) argued that the rise of FinTech firms in Indonesia led to reduced profitability for traditional banks due to heightened competition. Boot *et al.* (2021) also noted that digital platforms and new communication channels might weaken traditional banking models, suggesting that banks must adapt to remain competitive.

The development of FinTech indices has emerged as a critical tool for measuring technological integration in the banking sector. Cheng and Qu (2020) constructed a banking FinTech index using web crawlers and word frequency analysis to assess FinTech adoption trends. Similarly, Lee *et al.* (2023) utilized Baidu search engine data to track keyword frequencies related to FinTech, creating the Chinese banking FinTech index. However, while these indices provide valuable insights, they often focus on broad metrics and may lack specificity regarding operational efficiency and bank profitability.

Empirical studies also present mixed results regarding the profitability gains from FinTech, often influenced by regional and institutional factors. For example, Lee *et al.*, (2021) found that FinTech positively impacts bank profitability in China, particularly in asset quality management and efficiency. Conversely, Phan *et al.*, (2020) highlighted the challenges faced by small banks in adopting FinTech, which can lead to minimal or negative profitability outcomes. Zhao *et al.* (2022) emphasized that large banks benefit more significantly from FinTech due to their ability to scale and integrate advanced technologies.

Gai *et al.*, (2018) emphasized FinTech's crucial role in enhancing the quality of banking services through advanced information technology. Bakar *et al.* (2020) analyzed how FinTech investments in Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand influence bank performance in Southeast Asia, suggesting that strategic investment in FinTech can significantly boost financial outcomes. Similarly, Subanidja *et al.*, (2022) provide empirical evidence from Indonesia, demonstrating the substantial impact of FinTech on sustainable banking performance.

Other studies have focused on the collaborative aspects of FinTech (Elia *et al.*, 2023), examining how collaborations between banks and FinTech firms affect banking performance, with a particular focus on the moderating role of regulatory frameworks. Bashayreh and Wadi (2021) found that FinTech services positively impacted the performance of commercial banks in Jordan, as measured by return on equity (ROE).

A review of the literature on the relationship between FinTech and bank profitability reveals significant variations based on bank size. Large banks tend to benefit the most from FinTech innovations, enjoying increased profitability through enhanced operational efficiency, expanded customer bases, and new revenue streams (Zhao *et al.*, (2022). Medium-sized banks, while also seeing gains from FinTech, often face challenges related to scalability and resource constraints, limiting their ability to fully capitalize on these technologies (Katsiampa *et al.*, 2022). However, small banks frequently struggle with the high costs of integration and limited technological infrastructure, which can result in minimal profitability gains or even negative outcomes (Phan *et al.*, 2020). These findings highlight the need for bank-size-specific strategies in FinTech deployment to address the unique challenges and opportunities of each bank category effectively.

In the African context, studies have highlighted the transformative potential of FinTech. Haabazoka (2019) identified a positive correlation between FinTech applications, such as ATMs and mobile banking, and profitability in Zambian banks. Similarly, Odawa (2016) and Makina (2019) reported profitability gains from Internet and mobile banking in Kenya. However, Ky (2019) noted that the positive impact of FinTech in East African banks is primarily confined to mobile money services, leaving other FinTech innovations underexplored.

The literature review highlights a research gap in evaluating the relationship between bank profitability and the bank FinTech index within an emerging market such as Tanzania. Existing studies often focus on specific technologies or regions, leaving the broader implications of FinTech adoption underexplored. This study addresses these gaps by testing two hypotheses: (H₁) the development of financial technology, as measured by a bank FinTech index, positively influences the profitability of Tanzanian commercial banks; and (H₂) the positive effect of financial technology on profitability is moderated by bank size, with larger banks experiencing greater gains compared to medium and small banks. These hypotheses aim to provide nuanced insights into how FinTech integration drives bank profitability in Tanzania.

Methodology

Data and Study Design

This study examined the influence of the bank FinTech index on the profitability of commercial banks in Tanzania. Anchored by a positivist philosophy, this study empirically examines the relationship between the bank FinTech index and profitability, focusing on quantifiable data and objective analysis to ensure valid and reliable conclusions. This study utilized a balanced panel dataset spanning 2010 to 2021. Data were sourced from the Bank of Tanzania Supervision Information System (BSIS), which compiles annual audited financial statements from commercial banks. Additionally,

macroeconomic data were retrieved from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Bank of Tanzania (BOT), and World Bank indicators.

A purposive sample of 30 commercial banks is selected from an initial pool of 36. The selection was based on two criteria: continuous operation from 2010 to 2021 and complete financial and operational data availability for this period. Commercial banks are ideal for studying FinTech's influence on profitability in Tanzania because of their central role in financial intermediation and regulatory consistency, which provides a reliable basis for analyzing this relationship. The year 2010 was chosen as the starting point because of the enactment of the Electronic and Postal Communications Act, which significantly influenced the Fintech landscape in Tanzania (BOT, 2019). Furthermore, the widespread adoption of FinTech in Tanzania, beginning in 2008, transformed banking channels. By 2010, with significant growth in mobile and internet banking, it marked the early phase of FinTech integration (Macha & Massawe, 2023). Starting our research in 2010 allows us to analyze its long-term impact on banks' profitability as technology evolves.

The Bank of Tanzania classifies commercial banks into three peer groups based on total assets: peer group 1 includes the largest banks with assets ranging from TZS 500 billion to TZS 99.999 trillion; peer group 2 consists of medium-sized banks with assets between TZS 200 billion and TZS 500 billion; and peer group 3 comprises smaller banks with assets from TZS 30 billion to TZS 200 billion (BOT, 2018). These banks are categorized as large, medium, and small to reflect differences in resources, technological capabilities, and operational strategies that influence FinTech integration. Large banks typically possess a greater capacity for implementing advanced FinTech solutions, whereas medium and small banks may experience resource limitations but demonstrate distinct adoption patterns. This classification facilitates an analysis of whether the Bank FinTech Index's impact differs across bank sizes, offering valuable insights for policy formulation and strategic management (Lee *et al.*, 2021).

This study acknowledges the potential for survivorship bias, given that the sample consists of 30 commercial banks with complete data spanning 2010 to 2021, while six banks were excluded due to missing data. To address this concern, a robustness test was performed using Yield-Earning Assets (YEA) as an alternative measure of profitability. These adjustments strengthen the reliability and generalizability of the findings, ensuring a comprehensive analysis of FinTech's role in enhancing earnings within Tanzanian commercial banks. Table 1 provides details on the sample of commercial banks included in the study.

Table 1. Sample of Commercial Banks

Population of Commercial Banks	36
Number of commercial banks with missing data	(6)
Number of commercial banks with data	30
Period	(2010–2021) 11 years
Bank-year observations	360

A two-step System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) estimator was employed to assess the influence of the bank FinTech index on bank profitability. A panel research

design was employed to examine the trends in bank profitability over time with the bank FinTech index. This design is particularly suited for analyzing temporal trends, controlling for individual bank heterogeneity, and enhancing statistical robustness (Yitayaw, 2021). This technique addresses potential endogeneity and unobserved bank-specific effects, providing robust insights into the dynamic interplay between a bank's FinTech index and profitability in Tanzania's banking sector (Roodman, 2009).

Operationalisation of Research Variable

In this study, the selection of variables was a critical process that ensured the accuracy and relevance of the analysis. This selection is informed by a review of the existing literature, theoretical frameworks, and empirical evidence. Each variable, including the dependent, independent, and control variables, was operationalized as presented in table 2.

Table 2. Operationalisation of Research Variables

Variable	Operationalisation	Measurement	Empirical Evidence
Independent Variable		Composite Index	Wang <i>et al.</i> (2021b), Xie <i>et al.</i> , (2020),
FinTech Index (FTI)	The author owns FinTech index computation		
Dependent Variables			Phan <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Return Asset (ROA _{it})	Profit before tax divided by average total assets	Ratio	
Return on Equity (ROE _{it})	Net income divided by average total equity	Ratio	
Yield Earning Asset (YEA _{it})	Interest income divided by average earning assets	Ratio	
Control Variables			Phan <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Wang <i>et al.</i> (2021b) Singh <i>et al.</i> , (2021), (Sinaga <i>et al.</i> , 2020), (Kartikasary <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Cost to Income Ratio (CTI)	Operating expenses divided by operating income	Ratio	
Loan to Deposit Ratio (LDR)	Total loans divided by total deposits	Ratio	
Capital Adequacy ratio (CAR)	Total equity divided by total assets	Ratio	
Non-Performing Loans (NPLs)	Total NPLs divided by gross total loans	Ratio	
Bank Size	Logarithm of total assets	Ratio	
Inflation (INF)	Annual inflation rate (measured as a percentage change in consumer price index) of a country	Ratio	
Gross Domestic Product (GDP)	Annual GDP growth rate (%) of a country	Ratio	

The construction of the Bank FinTech Index

Following the approach of Kharrat *et al.* (2024) and Wang *et al.*, (2021a), this study details the construction of the FinTech index and key computational steps, highlighting methodological differences tailored to the Tanzanian context. FinTech data were gathered via an Excel checklist sent to banks, covering nine FinTech dimensions based on Wang *et al.* (2021), and adapted for Tanzania, resulting in thirty-three (33) specific FinTech applications (see Appendix 1). The nine dimensions and their associated thirty-three FinTech applications were tailored to align with the specific context of Tanzanian banks. Banks were required to annually indicate the presence of each application under the respective dimension, assigning a value of one (1) for available applications and zero (0) for those unavailable in a given year. Before calculating the index, diagnostic tests were used to confirm the adequacy of the sample. Scale reliability analysis showed high internal consistency (0.9818), and a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of 0.9472 indicated suitability for factor analysis (Durak *et al.*, 2024; Anita *et al.*, 2023; Theiri and Alareeni, 2023). With these reliability measures, the data were prepared for factor analysis, as shown in table 3.

Table 3. KMO and Cronbach’s Test Results

Test scale = mean (unstandardized items)	
Average interitem covariance:	0.117698
Number of items in the scale:	33
Scale reliability coefficient:	0.9818
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy (KMO)	0.9472

Principal component analysis (PCA) was used to simplify the dataset by identifying key patterns among the 33 FinTech applications (Kharrat *et al.*, 2024; Zheng *et al.*, 2024; Rizvi *et al.*, 2024) PCA, a multivariate technique, reduces data dimensionality by extracting principal components, highlighting essential factors within FinTech dimensions for clearer interpretation. Similar approaches have been effectively applied by Kharrat *et al.* (2024), enabling data simplification while retaining critical information (Rahman, 2024).

Several key steps were performed using PCA to compute the FinTech index. First, the covariance or correlation matrix was calculated from standardized data with n observations and p variables, illustrating the relationships between variables (Baak *et al.*, 2020). The covariance matrix was calculated as follows:

$$\sum = \frac{1}{n - 1} X^T \tag{1}$$

Where;

X = Standardised data with n observations

X^T = Denotes the transpose of X

Second, principal components were extracted from the covariance matrix using PCA. Each principal component is a linear combination of the original variables, capturing the maximum variance, with subsequent components explaining progressively less variance (Artoni et al., 2018). The principal components are computed as follows:

$$PC_k = XV_k \quad (2)$$

Where;

PC_k . = Principal components

V = Matrix of eigenvectors obtained from the covariance matrix.

V_k = Matrix of the first k eigenvectors corresponding to the largest eigenvalues.

The third step involves computing scores for each principal component for every bank, representing the data projection onto these components (Zhong and Enke, 2017). If X_i represent the data for bank i and PC_k is the k th principal component, the score for bank i on component k is calculated as;

$$Score_{ik} = X_i * PC_k \quad (3)$$

Fourth, each principal component was evaluated to determine the variance. The first component explains the most variance, with subsequent components explaining progressively less variance. Components with eigenvalues greater than one were retained. Finally, the composite bank FinTech index is computed by combining the retained components (Dasilas and Karanović, 2023). This involves multiplying each component by its corresponding weight and then summing these weighted values. We compute the FinTech index as follows:

$$FI = \sum_{k=1}^m Score_{ik} \times W_k \quad (4)$$

Where;

W_k = Weight of each retained component PC_k

m =Number of retained principal components

The resulting bank FinTech index offers a composite measure of FinTech development among Tanzanian commercial banks. This method is supported by literature from (Kharrat et al. (2024), Zheng et al. (2024), and Yao and Song (2023), highlighting PCA's effectiveness of PCA in reducing dimensionality and capturing essential variability in datasets.

Model Specification

This study examines the relationship between the bank FinTech index and the profitability of commercial banks using panel data from 2010-2021. This study employs a two-step system Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), a robust estimation technique capable of handling problems such as autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity (Blundell and Bond, 1998; Arellano and Bover, 1995). GMM comes in two main forms: difference GMM and system GMM, each of which has one- and two-step variations. The system GMM, particularly the two-step variant, is better suited to addressing issues such as heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation, as demonstrated in the studies by Khan *et al.*, (2024) and Ogbonna *et al.*, (2023). Thus, this study adopts a two-step system GMM for its estimations, a method that has proven effective in similar research (Dasilas and Karanović, 2023). The linear model for the dynamic GMM system applied in this study is as follows:

$$ROE_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FTI_{i,t} + \beta_2 CAR_{i,t} + \beta_3 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_4 CTI_{i,t} + \beta_5 NPL_{i,t} + \beta_6 LDR_{i,t} + \beta_7 GDP_t + \beta_8 INF_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (5)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FTI_{i,t} + \beta_2 CAR_{i,t} + \beta_3 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_4 CTI_{i,t} + \beta_5 NPL_{i,t} + \beta_6 LDR_{i,t} + \beta_7 GDP_t + \beta_8 INF_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (6)$$

Where; ROA = return on assets; ROE= return on equity; *FTI*= financial technology (Fintech) index; *CAR*= capital adequacy ratio; *SIZE*= bank size; *CTI*= cost to income ratio; *NPL*=non-performing loans; *LDR*=loans deposit ratio; *GDP*= gross domestic product; *INF*= inflation rate; α = constant term; $\beta_1 - \beta_{11}$ denotes coefficients of the variables; ε = error term; i = banks 1,2,..., and t =time in years.

In addition to the traditional metrics employed (ROA and ROE), this study incorporated the yield on earnings Assets (YEA_{it}) to conduct a robustness test. The YEA_{it} provides insight into the revenue-generating capacity of a bank's interest-earning assets, such as loans and investments, while ignoring non-earning assets (Dasilas and Karanović, 2023; Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021). This provides a more precise assessment of profitability related only to banks' core financial intermediation activities. The regression model is expressed as follows:

$$YEA_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 FTI_{i,t} + \beta_2 CAR_{i,t} + \beta_3 SIZE_{i,t} + \beta_4 CTI_{i,t} + \beta_5 NPL_{i,t} + \beta_6 LDR_{i,t} + \beta_7 GDP_t + \beta_8 INF_t + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

Where: $YEA_{i,t}$ = Yield Earning Asset of bank i in year t , while the rest of all variables and characters are as defined in Equation (5)

Diagnostic Tests

First, the data were examined for potential multicollinearity among independent variables to avoid distortions in the results. Additionally, tests were performed to address the unique characteristics of the panel data, including cross-sectional dependence and stationarity. Hansen and Sargan tests were also employed to validate the instruments used in the model, ensuring that they were not correlated with the error term, thereby providing unbiased and reliable estimations.

Pairwise Correlations and Multicollinearity Results

Table 4 presents the pairwise correlations and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) results for the bank FinTech index, control variables, and profitability. Correlations ranged from weak to moderate, with no values exceeding 0.85. This indicates a satisfactory level of distinction between the variables and a minimal risk of multicollinearity. This suggests that multicollinearity is not a significant concern in our model, as no independent variable's variance is excessively inflated due to correlations with other predictors (Asongu *et al.*, (2021). This method aligns with the approaches adopted by Kashif *et al.*, (2024) and Aggarwal *et al.*, (2023). The results of pairwise correlations and multicollinearity are presented in table 4.

Table 4. Correlations and Multicollinearity Results

Variables	ROA	ROE	YEA	FTI	CAR	lnSize	CTI	LDR	GDP	INF	NPL
(1) ROA	1.000										
(2) ROE	0.769 ^a	1.000									
(3) YEA	-0.021	-0.094 ^c	1.000								
(4) FTI	0.077	-0.003	0.069	1.000							
(5) CAR	-0.447 ^a	-0.192 ^a	0.090 ^c	-0.061	1.000						
(6) Size	0.493 ^a	0.328 ^a	-0.066	0.314 ^a	-0.648 ^a	1.000					
(7) CTI	-0.817 ^a	-0.587 ^a	-0.110 ^b	-0.136 ^b	0.373 ^a	-0.491 ^a	1.000				
(8) LDR	-0.267 ^a	-0.204 ^a	0.274 ^a	0.050	0.594 ^a	-0.430 ^a	0.107 ^b	1.000			
(9) GDP	0.038	0.113 ^b	0.017	-0.554 ^a	0.030	-0.106 ^b	0.023	-0.013	1.000		
(10) INF	-0.070	0.053	-0.138 ^b	-0.537 ^a	0.046	-0.165 ^b	0.133 ^b	-0.072	0.221 ^a	1.000	
(11) NPL	-0.237 ^a	-0.291 ^a	0.183 ^a	0.148 ^b	0.024	-0.014	0.172 ^b	0.082	-0.131 ^b	-0.217 ^a	1.000
VIF		1.79	1.18	2.22	2.37	2.37	2.12	1.82	1.52	1.51	1.19
1/VIF		0.558	0.849	0.450	0.422	0.422	0.471	0.55	0.657	0.664	0.840
Mean VIF	1.81										

^{a b c} Refers to the level of significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively

Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) ranging from 1.18 to 2.37, further confirm low to moderate multicollinearity (Sulaiman *et al.*, 2021; Gokmen *et al.*, 2022). The results shown in Table 4 reveal that all VIF values are below the threshold, with reciprocal VIFs (0.558 to 0.840) and a mean VIF of 1.83, indicating no multicollinearity issues among the study variables. This confirms the credibility and suitability of the data for further analysis.

Hansen and Sargan Tests

Hansen and Sargan tests verify the validity of the instruments used in the GMM framework, ensuring that the instruments are exogenous and uncorrelated with the error term, reducing the risk of biased parameter estimates (Blundell and Bond, 1998; Arellano and Bover, 1995). Endogeneity, a critical concern in panel data analysis, is mitigated by using lagged variables of the explanatory variables as instruments, addressing reverse causality and omitting variable bias for more reliable results (Sheraz *et al.*, 2022; Roodman, 2009). The test results confirm that the estimations are robust and valid. The AR (1) p-values (0.006, 0.060, and 0.012) indicate the expected first-order autocorrelation, which is typical and acceptable in dynamic-system GMM models

(Haiyun et al., 2023). The second-order autocorrelation AR (2) p-values (0.531, 0.385, and 0.464) show no significant second-order autocorrelation, thus fulfilling a critical requirement for the consistency of the GMM estimator (Haron et al., 2021). The Hansen test p-values (0.508, 0.226, and 0.332) suggest that the instruments used in the models were valid and appropriately specified, reinforcing the reliability of the results (Le et al., 2019). Overall, these tests collectively indicate that the models are well specified and the results are reliable.

Panel Cross-Sectional Dependency Tests

Table 5 presents the results of the cross-sectional dependency and panel unit root tests, using the Breusch-Pagan LM, Pesaran CD, and Friedman tests, as outlined by (Li *et al.*, 2024; Antwi and Kong, 2023). The detailed results for the cross-sectional dependence and panel unit root are presented in table 5.

Table 5. Tests of cross-sectional dependence and panel unit root (cross-sectionally augmented IPS)

Cross-section dependency (CD)			Cross-sectionally augmented IPS (CIPS) panel unit root			
	Breusch-Pagan LM test	Pesaran CD test	CIPS panel unit root		CIPS first difference	
Variables	Test statistics	Test statistics	Constant	Constant and trend	Constant	Constant and trend
ROA	770.613***	4.269***	-2.011	-2.770**		
ROE	754.089***	3.639***	-2.128*	-2.896***		
YEA	1960.939***	40.263***	-2.534***	-2.993***		
FTI	3503.384***	58.334***	-2.792***	-3.173***		
CAR	1331.610***	4.158***	-1.919	-2.311	-3.039***	-3.207***
lnSize	3344.896***	54.755***	-2.498***	-3.222***		
CTI	1038.758***	0.37	-2.236**	-3.001***		
GDP	5220***	72.250***	2.610***	1.7		
INF	5220***	72.250***	2.610***	1.7		
NPL	1252.372***	10.324***	-2.701***	-2.773**		
LDR	1175.317***	17.375***	-1.974	-1.837	-2.770***	-2.965 ***

Significance levels: *** 1%, ** 5%, * 10%.

Before performing the two-step system GMM analysis, the study checks for cross-sectional dependence, a typical feature in panel data where events such as regulatory changes can impact multiple banks (Shahbaz *et al.* 2023). Cross-sectional dependence tests, including the Breusch-Pagan LM, Pesaran CD, and Friedman's test, revealed significant dependence across all variables. Consequently, second-generation panel unit root tests were used to ensure accurate stationarity assessments in this context. The Cross-sectionally Augmented IPS (CIPS) test results show that capital adequacy ratio and loan to deposit ratio achieve stationarity after first differencing, indicating that they are

integrated in order one (I(1)), offering reliable outcomes (Shahbaz *et al.*, 2023). De Oliveira and Moutinho (2022).

Descriptive Statistics

Table 6 presents the descriptive results of the variables used to examine the influence of the bank FinTech index on the profitability of banks across different categories of commercial banks in Tanzania (All Banks, Large, Medium, and Small Banks). The FinTech Index (FTI) has a mean of 1.918 with a standard deviation of 2.175. Large banks exhibit a higher mean FTI of 2.544 (Std. Dev. = 2.162), which reflects a more advanced deployment of FinTech compared with medium banks (Mean = 1.476, Std. Dev. = 2.04) and small banks (Mean = 1.736, Std. Dev. = 2.194). This finding suggests that larger banks are better positioned to invest in and leverage financial technologies. The descriptive results for the variables are presented in table 6.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics Results

Variable	All Banks (360)		Large Banks (120)		Medium Banks (120)		Small Banks (120)	
	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean	Std. Dev.
ROA%	0.129	4.81	2.201	1.957	-0.365	5.139	-1.449	5.699
ROE%	3.097	20.769	11.598	10.539	2.364	23.063	-4.672	22.893
YEA%	9.767	4.895	7.77	1.878	8.986	2.987	12.544	6.886
FTI	1.918	2.175	2.544	2.162	1.476	2.04	1.736	2.194
CAR%	16.575	11.183	13.169	2.868	14.375	7.983	22.18	16.032
lnSize	11.465	0.841	12.113	0.346	11.445	0.342	10.837	1.038
CTI%	88.278	56.556	66.169	14.291	94.068	60.669	104.597	70.492
LDR%	81.565	48.771	67.003	16.475	82.143	23.422	95.55	77.1
GDP%	5.783	1.49	5.783	1.494	5.783	1.494	5.783	1.494
INF%	6.583	3.778	6.583	3.789	6.583	3.789	6.583	3.789
NPL	9.215	12.478	6.614	5.16	11.312	15.97	9.719	13.286

The analysis shows that large banks outperform smaller ones in asset utilization and equity returns, with a positive average ROA of 2.201% and ROE of 11.598%, compared with negative ROA and ROE for medium and small banks, indicating efficiency challenges. The cost-to-income Ratio (CTI) varies widely, with large banks maintaining a lower CTI, reflecting better cost management, while medium and small banks show higher ratios, suggesting operational inefficiencies. The Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) also varies, with small banks showing a higher LDR (95.55%) due to greater reliance on loans, whereas large banks manage a balanced LDR (67.003%). For the (CAR), small banks hold the strongest capital buffers (22.18%), while large banks operate with a lower CAR, indicating different capital management strategies.

Results and Discussion

Influence of a Bank FinTech Index on the Profitability of Commercial Banks

Table 7 panels 1 to 2 presents the two-step GMM system estimators results, the analysis reveals a strong and statistically significant positive relationship between a bank's FinTech index and profitability as measured by ROA and ROE. The detailed results for all three panels are indicated in table 6.

Table 7. Influence of a Bank FinTech Index (FTI) on Profitability as Measured by ROE, ROA

Variables	(1) ROA	(2) ROE	(3) YEA
L.DEP	0.124*** (0.034)	0.259*** (0.100)	0.737*** (0.030)
FTI	0.078* (0.043)	1.596*** (0.498)	0.254*** (0.035)
CAR	-0.057*** (0.019)	0.187* (0.111)	-0.030* (0.017)
lnBSize	-1.123 (0.735)	-3.532 (10.210)	-3.042*** (0.569)
CTI	-0.067*** (0.009)	-0.263*** (0.083)	-0.021*** (0.005)
LDR	-0.006*** (0.002)	-0.039 (0.028)	0.012*** (0.003)
GDP	0.114*** (0.026)	1.822*** (0.529)	-0.118*** (0.034)
INF	0.006 (0.021)	0.666*** (0.227)	-0.050** (0.020)
NPL	-0.035*** (0.005)	-0.160*** (0.056)	0.016* (0.009)
Constant	20.054** (9.381)	49.178 (129.823)	40.248*** (7.379)
Observations	330	330	330
Number of banks	30	30	30
AR (1)	0.006	0.060	0.012
AR (2)	0.531	0.385	0.464
Hansen	0.508	0.226	0.332
Sargen	0.139	0.069	0.011
Number of Instruments	25.000	21.000	25.000

Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

The results provide a detailed analysis of the influence of the bank FinTech index (FTI) on banks' profitability, focusing on two key measures: ROA and ROE.

Starting with ROA, the results show a positive coefficient of 0.078, which is statistically significant at the 10% level. This finding suggests that an increase in the FinTech index is linked to a corresponding increase in ROA, indicating that a bank's FinTech development enhances the efficiency of asset utilization. The use of FinTech enables the more effective management of loans, a key asset for banks, which can result

in higher profitability. Technologies, such as big data, artificial intelligence, and machine learning, improve the evaluation of loan applicants, thereby reducing credit risk. Additionally, mobile banking, mobile payments, and quick response code payments facilitate loan repayments and minimize default risk.

This increase in asset efficiency can be attributed to several factors. First, FinTech solutions streamline banking operations by automating routine tasks, reducing manual errors, and optimizing workflow. This not only lowers transaction costs, but also improves banks' ability to serve customers and maximize returns on their assets. Second, the integration of advanced Fintech tools for credit risk assessment and monitoring helps banks manage and mitigate lending risks more effectively. By reducing the occurrence of non-performing loans, banks can maintain healthier balance sheets, leading to better returns on their assets. These empirical outcomes are consistent with studies conducted by Kharrat et al., (2024) and Alshehadeh and Al-Khawaja (2022), who conclude that commercial banks' FinTech index positively improves their profitability of commercial banks.

The analysis also highlights the influence of the bank Fintech index on ROE, where the coefficient of 1.596 is highly significant at the 1% level. This strong positive relationship implies that banks with higher levels of Fintech development tend to generate higher returns for their shareholders. There are several reasons for this finding. One of the most critical factors is FinTech's ability to unlock new revenue streams (Zhao et al., 2022). Through digital banking services, mobile payments, and personalized financial products, banks can attract a broader customer base and increase their revenue. These additional income sources, when efficiently managed, translate into higher returns on equity. Furthermore, the efficiency gains from FinTech deployment play a crucial role in reducing operational costs. As banks streamline their processes and leverage technology to perform tasks more efficiently, they can better utilize their equity, thereby improving profitability.

Additionally, FinTech offers banks a strategic advantage by enabling them to stay competitive in a rapidly evolving financial landscape. FinTech in Tanzania's banking sector has transformed payments for services, such as electricity, transport, water, and television subscriptions. Through mobile and Internet banking, customers can easily pay for services from their devices. FinTech platforms offer real-time and secure payments, eliminate the need for physical visits, and boost financial inclusion. Additionally, these innovations have increased transaction volumes, thereby improving bank profitability through service fees and enhancing operational efficiency. These findings are consistent with the findings of Kharrat *et al.*, (2024) who concluded that a bank FinTech index positively affects the profitability of banks in the MENA region, further, Chhaidar *et al.*, (2023) concluded that FinTech is positively and significantly related to the bank profitability of 23 European banks, inferring that the greater the digital engagement of banks is, the higher the profitability is. The same was also documented by Yang *et al.* (2023), Chen *et al.* (2021), Wang *et al.*, (2021), Ozili *et al.* (2021a), and Phan *et al.*, (2020), who concluded that commercial banks' FinTech index positively influences the profitability of commercial banks in the UAE and the Chinese banking industry.

Influence of a Bank FinTech Index on the Profitability of Banks by Bank Categories

Table 8 provides an in-depth analysis of the influence of the bank FinTech index (FTI) on the profitability of banks, specifically focusing on ROA and ROE across small, medium, and large banks. The regression results, derived using a system GMM estimator, reveal varied effects of a bank's FinTech index on profitability measures depending on the bank's categories.

The analysis of ROA in Table 8 indicates that the influence of the bank FinTech index on bank profitability is not uniform across different bank sizes. For large banks, the FTI shows a positive and statistically significant coefficient of 0.527 at the 10% level, suggesting that a bank FinTech index enhances the efficiency of asset utilization in these banks, leading to improved profitability, as measured by ROA. This positive impact could be attributed to the ability of large banks to better absorb the costs associated with FinTech integration and leverage technology to optimize asset management and operational efficiency. Large banks are typically better equipped to invest in and fully integrate advanced FinTech solutions, allowing them to realize gains in asset utilization that contribute to higher profitability. These findings are consistent with findings from the study conducted by Dasilas and Karanović, (2023) who concluded that a bank FinTech index positively influences the profitability of large banks as measured by ROA. The detailed results for the bank categories measured by ROA and ROE are shown in table 8.

Table 8. Influence of a Bank FinTech Index (FTI) on the Profitability of Banks by Bank Categories

Variables	ROA			ROE		
	Small Banks	Medium Banks	Large Banks	Small Banks	Medium Banks	Large Banks
L.DEP	3.070** (1.355)	-0.276* (0.144)	-1.090** (0.477)	0.552** (0.253)	4.356*** (1.5920)	-1.481** (0.693)
FTI	-2.626 (2.437)	-2.381 (2.471)	0.527* (0.296)	-0.316 (5.844)	-62.754 (44.679)	7.628* (3.924)
CAR	-0.237 (0.296)	-0.584 (0.537)	0.004 (0.329)	1.735 (2.454)	2.167 (1.552)	-0.382 (1.885)
lnSize	-14.959 (22.72)	0.465 (5.972)	1.178** (0.498)	-4.685 (63.019)	57.811* (33.937)	8.046*** (2.29)
CTI	0.036 (0.07)	-0.066 (0.049)	-0.122* (0.071)	-0.015 (0.289)	-0.797* (0.478)	-1.212** (0.472)
LDR	0.079** (0.037)	0.031 (0.022)	0.015 (0.017)	-0.556 (0.586)	-0.418 (1.112)	0.318 (0.351)
GDP	-16.096** (7.826)	-0.815 (1.288)	0.386 (0.353)	5.385 (8.988)	-58.602 (41.477)	-1.885 (1.349)
INF	2.049 (2.015)	-0.536 (0.697)	-0.247 (0.185)	-2.854 (4.012)	21.085 (13.917)	-0.05 (0.423)

Variables	ROA			ROE		
	Small Banks	Medium Banks	Large Banks	Small Banks	Medium Banks	Large Banks
NPL	-2.498**	-0.057	-0.271	0.057	1.342***	4.118*
	(1.186)	(0.048)	(0.342)	(0.345)	(0.468)	(2.372)
Constant	267.224	18.424	0	54.98	0	0
	(277.07)	(78.167)	0	(735.816)	0	0
Observations	110	110	110	110	110	110
Number of banks	10	10	10	10	10	10
AR (1)	0.335	0.909	0.183	0.054	0.047	0.367
AR (2)	0.691	0.269	0.209	0.965	0.199	0.764
Hansen	1	1	0.483	1	0.931	0.999
Sargen	0.42	0.504	0.577	0.704	0.986	0.536
Number of Instruments	10	10	10	10	10	10

Standard errors in parentheses *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

When examining ROE, the results again show significant variability across bank sizes. For large banks, the FTI coefficient is positive at 7.628 and statistically significant at the 10% level, indicating that the FinTech index as a measure of banks' FinTech development enhances equity returns in large banks. This result is consistent with the idea that large banks, with their broader customer base, more extensive resources, and better economies of scale, can effectively utilize FinTech to enhance profitability and deliver higher returns to shareholders. The ability to introduce new digital products, optimize cost structures, and enhance customer engagement through FinTech provides large banks with a strategic advantage, contributing to improved ROE (Bashayreh and Wadi, 2021).

However, the results for small and medium-sized banks differ markedly. For medium banks, the FTI coefficient is negative (-62.754), but not statistically significant, indicating no clear evidence that a bank FinTech index benefits their equity returns. This could be due to the substantial costs associated with FinTech investment, which might strain banks' financial performance, especially if they lack the scale to efficiently implement and capitalize on new technologies. For small banks, the FTI coefficient is also negative but not significant, suggesting that the relationship between a bank's FinTech index and ROE is not straightforward. Small banks might be at a disadvantage because of limited resources, which can make it difficult to achieve the same level of returns from FinTech investments as their larger counterparts' banks. These findings align with the study conducted by Keliuotyte-Staniulienė and Smolskytė, (2019) in Lithuania who concludes the effect of financial technology development in small and medium banks is not significant.

These findings suggest that the influence of a bank's FinTech on profitability is highly contingent on bank size. Large banks appear to be better positioned to leverage FinTech for profitability, particularly to enhance ROE, because of their greater ability to invest in technology, manage integration costs, and exploit economies of scale (Dasilas and Karanović, 2023; Song *et al.*, 2023; Zinakova, 2020). By contrast, small and medium

banks face challenges in realizing profitability benefits from FinTech, as shown by the non-significant or negative FTI coefficients in their ROA and ROE regressions. Higher costs, integration difficulties, and slower benefit realization may limit FinTech's impact on profitability. These findings emphasize the importance of considering bank size in assessing FinTech profitability effects and suggest that smaller banks may need tailored strategies to maximize FinTech benefits.

After discussing the bank FinTech index and its effect on profitability, section 4.3, the study examines the influence of bank-specific and macroeconomic factors on the profitability of Tanzanian commercial banks. This analysis provides a better understanding of the factors that drive bank profitability in Tanzania.

Influence of Bank-Specific and Macroeconomic Factors on the Profitability of Banks

To gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing bank profitability in Tanzanian commercial banks, this study not only analyzed the influence of the bank FinTech index but also explored the relationship between bank-specific and macroeconomic factors and their effects on profitability. Table 6 presents the results for all the combined banks. The results reveal that the (CAR) shows a significant effect, with a negative coefficient for ROA (-0.057) and significance at the 1% level, indicating that higher capital adequacy might slightly reduce profitability by leading banks to hold safer, low-yield assets. The same results were documented by Al Mamun *et al.*, (2022), who conclude that capital adequacy negatively influences ROA banks in Bangladesh. However, the positive coefficient for ROE (0.187) is significant at the 10% level, suggesting that greater capital adequacy enhances equity returns, likely because of the improved financial stability and lower risk premiums associated with well-capitalized banks. The Cost-to-Income Ratio (CTI) exhibits coefficients of -0.067 significant at the 1% level for ROA and -0.263 significant at the 1% level for ROE. This indicates that as the CTI increases, the bank's operating costs rise relative to its income, and both ROA and ROE decrease. In other words, higher operational costs negatively impact profitability in terms of both asset utilization (ROA) and returns to shareholders (ROE). The stronger negative coefficient for ROE suggests that cost management is crucial for maximizing equity returns, making efficient operations essential for overall banking financial performance.

Thus, Banks that control costs relative to income are more likely to achieve higher profitability, consistent with the findings of Saif-Alyousfi (2022), Derbali (2021), and Paltrinieri *et al.*, (2021). The regression results show that the Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR) negatively impacts ROA (-0.006) at the 1% significance level, indicating that more aggressive lending slightly reduces asset profitability, while its effect on ROE (-0.039) is negative but not significant. GDP positively affects both ROA (0.114) and ROE (1.822) at the 1% level, suggesting that economic growth enhances profitability, particularly equity returns, by increasing business opportunities and lowering credit risks. This supports Shoaib Khan (2022), who found that GDP positively affects bank ROA in GCC countries. Additionally, Non-Performing Loans negatively affect both ROA (-0.035) and ROE (-0.160) at a 1% significance level, underscoring the importance of FinTech in reducing credit risk, consistent with Siddique *et al.*, (2022), on banks in South Asia.

After analyzing the influence of bank-specific and macroeconomic factors on the profitability of all combined banks, the study further examined these influences by categorizing banks to gain deeper insights into the relationships. The results presented in Table 7 highlight the relationship between these factors and the profitability of banks across different categories, as measured by ROA and ROE. The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) generally shows no significant impact on ROA or ROE, although there are slight variations in the coefficients, with large banks exhibiting a positive but insignificant relationship with ROA (0.004) and a negative but insignificant impact on ROE (-0.382). Bank size plays a more pronounced role, particularly for large banks, where a significant positive effect on both ROA (1.178) at the 5% level and ROE (8.046) is significant at the 1% level, suggesting that larger banks benefit from economies of scale and greater market power. This observation is supported by studies conducted by Kirimi *et al.* (2022) and Derbali (2021), who conclude that bank size positively impacts the ROA and ROE of commercial banks in Kenya and Morocco, respectively. Conversely, small banks struggle to convert size into profitability, as indicated by the negative coefficients of both ROA and ROE.

Furthermore, the regression results in Table 6 indicate a negative relationship between the Cost-to-Income Ratio (CTI) and both ROA and ROE across various bank categories. Specifically, the negative and statistically significant coefficients for medium and large banks in ROE (-0.797 and -1.212) significant at 10% and 5%, respectively, for medium and large banks suggest that as the CTI increases, higher operating costs relative to income profitability decrease, particularly in terms of returns to shareholders. For ROA, the negative but less significant coefficients (-0.066 and -0.122) indicate a similar trend, although the impact on ROE is more pronounced. This relationship underscores the importance of cost management in enhancing bank profitability, especially in larger banks where operational efficiency is crucial for maximizing equity returns. Akonye *et al.*, (2022) on Nigerian banks documented the negative impact of the Cost-to-Income Ratio (CTI) on ROA and ROE in Nigerian banks.

Macroeconomic variables show varied effects, with GDP negatively impacting ROA in small banks (-16.096) at the 5% significance level, while having no effect on ROE across all bank sizes. The negative impact of GDP on ROA in small banks in Tanzania may stem from their limited resources and heightened competition, which makes it challenging for them to capitalize on economic growth. Larger banks with stronger networks tend to capture more profitable opportunities during an economic expansion, leaving smaller banks with less favorable or riskier businesses, further reducing their returns on assets.

Non-performing loans (NPLs) significantly reduce ROA in small banks, indicating the profitability challenges that they face from bad Loans. Interestingly, a positive and significant relationship between NPLs and ROE is observed in medium and large banks, suggesting that these banks may engage in higher risk-taking by lending to riskier borrowers at higher interest rates to temporarily boost ROE, a trend also seen in Nigerian banks, as noted by Michael and Enang (2022). However, this approach could pose long-term risks, as accumulating NPLs may eventually weaken banks' financial stability, leading to future losses and a potential decline in the ROE.

Robustness Tests

To further validate the results for ROA and ROE, the yield on earning assets (YEA) was used as an alternative profitability measure. Table 6 shows a positive, significant coefficient of 0.254 at the 1% level for the bank FinTech index (FTI) with the YEA, indicating that FinTech development significantly boosts banks' income from assets. This enhancement likely results from optimized asset management, where FinTech tools improve asset allocation and investment strategies and increase returns. Additionally, Fintech enhances customer engagement by enabling more personalized services, further improving asset performance and yields. The significant positive coefficients of 0.124 for ROA, 0.259 for ROE, and 0.254 for YEA in the lagged variables (all at the 1% level) indicate strong profitability persistence. This suggests that banks with a history of profitability are likely to remain profitable, especially in the ROE, because of retained earnings and reinvestment. When combined with the FinTech index, these findings imply that FinTech-driven efficiency and risk management reinforce and sustain profitability, supporting banks in maintaining and improving their financial performance over time.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study underscores that effective FinTech integration significantly enhances profitability for Tanzanian commercial banks, particularly large banks, by driving operational efficiency, optimizing asset utilization, and generating new revenue streams. However, small and medium banks experience limited gains due to resource constraints and infrastructure challenges. These findings align with prior studies demonstrating FinTech's positive impact on profitability in large banks but diverge from research suggesting uniform benefits across all bank sizes (Dasilas and Karanović, 2023). This study contributes to the literature by addressing these contradictions and highlighting the need for context-specific approaches to FinTech adoption. Policymakers should establish a supportive regulatory framework, incentivize partnerships between smaller banks and FinTech firms, and introduce capacity-building programmes to bridge resource and infrastructure gaps. Practitioners, particularly in small and medium banks, should adopt tailored strategies, including scalable FinTech solutions and robust risk management practices, to address inefficiencies and reduce non-performing loans. By focusing on these targeted interventions, banks can ensure sustainable profitability across all categories while maximizing the potential of FinTech to transform banking operations.

Recommendations

Banks should establish innovation teams to identify opportunities where FinTech can improve efficiency, asset utilization, and profitability. Large banks can leverage advanced technologies like big data, machine learning, artificial intelligence and blockchain among others, while small and medium banks should prioritize collaborations with FinTech providers to adopt scalable, cost-effective solutions. Capacity-building through training and knowledge-sharing is essential for successful integration. The Bank of Tanzania should create a supportive regulatory framework, including tax incentives, funding for innovation, and policies encouraging partnerships between banks and FinTech firms. Developing a FinTech ecosystem through accelerators and public-private collaborations will further drive innovation, ensuring banks of all sizes enhance profitability and

competitiveness.

Study implications, limitations and direction for future studies

Theoretical implication

This study contributes to the theoretical discourse by integrating the Financial Innovation Theory (FIT) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to examine the relationship between the Bank FinTech Index and profitability in Tanzanian banks. It extends FIT by empirically validating the positive impact of FinTech innovations on bank profitability, particularly in larger banks, where technologies such as mobile banking, internet banking, and big data analytics among others enhance operational efficiency and asset utilization. Additionally, it introduces moderating factors such as bank size, cost management, and capital adequacy, broadening FIT's applicability to diverse banking environments and emphasizing the importance of aligning FinTech adoption strategies with bank-specific characteristics. The inclusion of TAM complements this perspective by addressing behavioral and organizational factors, such as perceived usefulness (PU) and ease of use (PEOU), which are essential for successful FinTech adoption. By highlighting the role of user-friendly and beneficial technologies, the study emphasizes how these factors drive smoother integration and maximize profitability. By applying these frameworks to the Tanzanian context, the study validates their relevance in emerging markets while addressing resource and regulatory challenges. These insights offer actionable guidance for policymakers and practitioners to leverage FinTech for enhanced profitability and financial stability in the banking sector.

Limitations and areas for further studies

This study addresses a critical gap in understanding FinTech's impact on banking profitability in Tanzania, but several limitations should be noted. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to analyze long-term trends, suggesting that future research could adopt longitudinal approaches to capture evolving dynamics. The reliance on secondary data, while effective for quantifying trends, does not fully explore qualitative aspects such as organizational culture or customer adoption barriers. Future studies could address this by integrating mixed methods for a more comprehensive analysis.

Author Contributions

The following authors were involved in the drafting of this paper and specific tasks performed are narrated below:

Omary Juma Ally 1*: Conceived and designed the study, collected, and analyzed data, and wrote the initial draft of the manuscript. Contributed to the literature review and provided valuable insights into the theoretical framework and was a major contributor to writing the manuscript.

Yusuph Kulindwa: Contributed to the study design, performed statistical analysis, and critically revised the manuscript for intellectual content. Participated in manuscript editing and proofreading of the document.

Lucas Mataba: Provided subject matter expertise, contributed to data interpretation, and assisted in revising the manuscript for clarity and accuracy. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

All authors have read and approved the final manuscript of the version to be published and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the research undertaken in this study.

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Appendix

FinTech Variable Dimensions and Applications

Dimension	FinTech Applications				
Payment	Mobile Payments	Third-Party Payments	QR Code Payments	Remittances	POS
Resource Allocation	Internet Loans	Network Investments	Online Lending's	P2PLoans	
Risk Management	Internet Insurance	Online Financing	Regtech and Suptech	e-KYC	Digital ID
Network Channel	Mobile Banking	Online Banking Service	Agency Banking	Internet Banking	
Big data	Bigdata	Data Mining	Bigdata analysis	Big Data Application	
Artificial Intelligence	Intelligent Robot	Artificial Intelligence	Machine Learning		
Distributed Technology	Cloud Computing	Block Chain Technology			
Internet Technology	Vehicle Interconnection	Wireless	Mobile Internet	Mobile Communication	
Security Technology	Biometrics	Fingerprint Identification			

As adopted from: (Wang *et al.*, 2023; Wu *et al.*, 2023; Lv *et al.*, 2022; Wang *et al.*, 2021;

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